

Improving the level of speaking skill through FRET Strategy

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ABSTRACT

The research centers on the effectiveness of the FRET Strategy as an intervention in the development of the speaking skill at DFLOMNHSS – SHS whereas HUMSS 11-D students' struggles on speaking English language during their Oral Communication class. Hence, this can negatively impact their performance in class. To determine the students' level of speaking skill, the researcher used mixed method of research, specifically focusing on Grade 11 HUMSS D Students enrolled in the SY 2023-2024. The researcher used the validated researcher-made pre-test and post-test rubric to collect the data needed in order to answer the specific problems of this study whereas the results showed that the students obtained a mean score of 10.15 in the pre-test interpreted as Below Basic and 14.99 in the posttest interpreted as Basic using statistical treatment and thematic analysis. These findings highlight the effectiveness of FRET Strategy in improving the speaking skill and stress the emergence of implementing the conceptual model in using FRET Strategy dubbed as FILL. Furthermore, it provides valuable insights into the ongoing discourse on language anxiety and how it impacts language acquisition in educational settings.

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INTRODUCTION

Public speaking is a fundamental aptitude an individual must have, particularly in school. It allows learners to actively engage themselves in class and participate in teaching-learning process. In the Philippines, students are taught to speak in their native tongue, the country's lingua franca, which is Filipino, and English. In the classroom, teachers use these mediums as the teaching and learning process goes on. Students who are not even native to Filipino or English must learn these languages. With that, problems are encountered (Gandeza, 2023).

Hashemi, 2020 stated that, "language anxiety is intrinsically found among language learners when learning a new language." Further, this topic is therefore an imperative issue in enhancing the development of skills in the target language in the modern language classroom environment. As cited by Lungay 2023, "this is a challenge for not only the learners, but also the teachers." Hence, it is important to note that the language teachers are often non-native speakers who may experience language anxiety themselves (Kralova, Skorvagova, Tirpakova & Markechova, 2017).

Based on the class observation at DFLOMNHS – SHS, students may have thoughts in mind but to keep up with squeezing these thoughts, an individual should appropriately learn to organize contemplations. In reality, not everyone has this capacity which causes them to involvement trouble in communicating with other individuals or in a swarm which regularly comes out in public speaking anxiety. In expansion, side impacts of uneasiness incorporate stress, uneasiness, trembling, sweating, shaking, wooziness, sweat, and stammering of voice. (Lungay, 2023).

With that, the researcher came up to improving the speaking skill of Grade 11 HUMSS D students of DFLOMNHS through the use of FRET Strategy which was developed by (Gandeza, 2023) whereas FRET is an oral language improvement program that provides participants with the confidence to talk clearly and expound on their views. Whilst language fillers is used to express themselves boldly and fluently, it also aids individuals composure, distinctive style, and pay attention with the appropriate emotions to offer certain thoughts, facts, and concepts while reducing anxiety.

Additionally, the researcher identified a gap in the study; particularly in the application of the intervention that was used for only two weeks, which is not recommendable in order to obtain more reliable results. Anent to this, language fillers researches are also lacking as it was seen as a natural dilemma and not a problem. Hence, this is something that the researcher wanted to fill. Moreover, this research will not only serve as an eye opener that language fillers can be used to aid students problem in speaking but also helps to aid the lack of research on language fillers. In essence, mastering filler word usage becomes a multifaceted tool that enhances cognitive processes, self-expression, and overall communication skills for students in academic and personal contexts.

Through it, when the researcher served as their pre-service teacher, it turned out that a teacher should not only teach the students' from the book but also from the heart. Whilst, this can either have a good or bad impact on the students' learning experiences, the researcher led to the development of the conceptual model in using FRET Strategy to avoid such negative impacts. The mechanisms in the acronym FILL stands for "*Following K to 12 Curriculum*", "*Identifying Learners Speaking Ability*", "*Letter of Approval*", and "*Let learners use FRET in delivering their answers*".

Aside from the favourable study findings, the researcher was inspired to apply it since the researcher had prior experience in public speaking as he was one of the moderators of an International organization whereas, the results of this study can be used by the school administrator of the said school in addressing the problem.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study determined the level of speaking skill of HUMSS 11-D students of DFLOMNHS during pre-test and post-test. It also ascertained the effective use of FRET Strategy in improving the speaking skill.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

In this study, the researcher conducted an action research to improve the speaking skill of Grade 11 HUMSS D students through FRET Strategy at DFLOMNHS San Blas, Bangar, La Union. The researcher utilized the descriptive design of research. Moreover, it made use of the mixed methods of qualitative and quantitative research process whereas these data provides valuable results in order to give a fuller and richer picture of the participants' experiences on using FRET Strategy. It also provides facts and scientific judgments may provide essential knowledge about the nature of objects and persons. This study was mixed method because it identified the level of speaking skill of Grade 11 HUMSS D learners at DFLOMNHS and it also determined the effectiveness of FRET Strategy as an intervention through a saturation process of interview which led to the development of a conceptual model in using FRET Strategy. This was also a two-shot mixed research since the researcher intended to find out the level of speaking skill using the pre-test and post-test to only one group of learners and the effectiveness of FRET Strategy using saturation process of interview.

Population and Location

In this research, the researcher narrowed the focus to 40 Grade 11 students who were currently taking Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand at DFLOMNHS. The researcher utilized total enumeration of the respondents to address the ethical considerations of this research – as the respondents were limited to specific grade level – the Grade 11 HUMSS D students. Anent to this was due to lack of financial resources of the researcher to test a larger population for the study. Moreover, the intervention was applied for two weeks only because of the limited time given to conduct the study.

Instrumentation

The researcher used the validated researcher-made pre-test and post-test rubric to collect the data needed in order to answer the specific problems of this study. A pre-test was an impromptu speech delivery provided to respondents before applying the intervention, whereas a post-test was given after applying it. The content of these impromptu questions must remain the same in order to establish whether or not any changes occurred. The said test was composed of 50 questions that were distributed one (1) question each and answered by the respondents individually with the use of rubrics to improve their level of speaking skill. These questions were personally taken by the researcher from lessons of the K to 12 Grade 11 Learner's Material in Oral Communication in Context to assure that the content of the test is appropriate to the readiness level of the respondents. Even though the book from which the researcher took the content of the test was made by experts, the researcher still asked for the help of the experts for the rubric validation of the said test to further check the appropriateness and coherence of the content.

Data Gathering Procedure, Analysis, and Ethical Considerations

In this study, the researcher goes through the following phases: *Problem Observation, Pre-test, Intervention, Post-test and Interview*; during the implementation of the FRET Strategy. On the first month of deployment, the researcher observed that learners are quiet whenever he asked questions to the learners regarding the topic or lesson being discussed. With that observation, the researcher came up on identifying their problem in speaking skill through the use of FRET Strategy. After a month of observation, the researcher used the validated

researcher-made pre-test to determine the level of speaking skill of the Grade 11 HUMSS D learners prior to the application of the intervention. After the pretest, the researcher then applied the FRET Strategy as an intervention. The researcher assured that the respondents could use language fillers so that they could achieve the objective of the strategy. One minute was given only in answering the said questions since it was an impromptu speaking. This was done during their Oral Communication class particularly on the application part. After the 10 days straight of applying the intervention, the researcher tested the level of speaking skill of the respondents through impromptu speaking and with the researcher-made post-test. The process that the researcher did in the pre- test was the same in the post-test, from organizing the respondents until giving instructions and delivering their answers. In determining the effectiveness of FRET Strategy, the researcher conducted an online interview among learners of the said grade level and strand about their experiences in using FRET Strategy. Saturation process was done by the researcher on a one-on-one online interview through the use of messenger application where the researcher stopped having the interview when the respondents had the same set of answers. Prior to this, the researcher also informed the respondents once again that the data gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

The data that was collected from the researcher-made pre-test and post-test was carefully recorded in tables, analyzed and interpreted accordingly based on the results of the statistical treatment. In this study, the researcher used the percentage distribution, mean and dependent t-test as statistical tools. Further, the researcher also utilized open-ended questions to determine the effectiveness of FRET Strategy as an intervention. Afterwards, the researcher used thematic analysis in interpreting the results of the interview.

During the teaching internship, the researcher asked permission to the Secondary School Principal IV of DFLOMNHS in conducting an action research, particularly to HUMSS 11 D Learners, through a letter. Once approved, the researcher informed his cooperating teacher and the learners on the conduct of this research prior to their pretest and posttest. The cooperating teacher and respondents willingly participated and voluntarily asked when the conduct of the research is.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part provides an overview of the results from a researcher-made pre-test and post-test administered at DFLOMNHS, encompassing a cohort of 40 Grade 11 HUMSS D participants.

Table 1. Level of Speaking Skill during Pretest and Post-Test

Scale of Scores	Pre-Test		Post-Test		... Description
	(F)	(P)	(F)	(P)	
21-25	2	5%	5	12.5%	Advanced
16-20	7	17.5%	13	32.5%	Proficient
11-15	8	20%	7	17.5%	Basic
6-10	8	20%	15	37.5%	... Below Basic
0-5	15	37.5%	0	0	Developing
Total:	40	100%	40	100%	
Mean:	10.15 Below Basic		14.99 Basic		

Specifically, as shown in table 1, in their pre-test, two of them obtained scores ranging from 21-25 interpreted as ‘Advanced’ which indicates that there was only 5% of the class who excelled in public speaking. This gave the researcher an idea that there was a need to implement immediately the FRET Strategy to aid the learners’ problem in speaking skill. Meanwhile, there are a total of seven (7) learners or 17.5% who got scores ranging from 16-20 interpreted as ‘Proficient’ which clearly showed that prior to the 5% advanced level of the learners, there are a higher percentage of the level of speaking skill. Hence, they must improve their language abilities, which “involve not only linguistic knowledge but also cultural understanding and interpersonal skills which proved that fillers are a helpful communication tactic as a result (Gandeza, 2023).

Moreover, a higher percentage was accumulated by the 8 learners or 20% who garnered scores ranging from 11-15 interpreted as 'Basic'. Likewise, there were also 8 learners or 20% who acquired scores ranging from 6-10 interpreted as 'Below Basic' where the finding implied that it was the second highest level of speaking skill of Grade 11 HUMSS D learners. Lastly, most of the learners, 15 of them or 37.5% got the score that ranges from 0-5 interpreted as 'Developing' to which it was shown in the table 1. As there was an increase in the percentage of the level of speaking skill of the learners, as shown in the table 1, the researcher opt to use the FRET strategy to aid the learners' problem in speaking skill. Prior to the implementation, the researcher then explained that the learners could use language fillers to effectively convey their ideas, thoughts, feelings and/or emotions.

On the other hand, on the post-test, 5 of the learners or 12.5% obtained scores ranging from 21-25 interpreted as 'Proficient' which showed that there was an increase after the intervention was applied. Meanwhile, there are a total of 13 learners or 32.5% who got scores ranging from 16-20 interpreted as 'Proficient'. There are 7 learners or 17.5% who garnered scores ranging from 11-15 interpreted as 'Basic'. Most of the learners, 15 of them, or 37.5% who acquired scores ranging from 6-10 interpreted as 'Below Basic'. Subsequently, none of them got the score that ranges from 0-5 interpreted as 'Developing' which proved based on the results shown in the table 1 that upon implementation of the FRET Strategy, learners were able to express their thoughts, feelings, emotions and/or ideas.

Generally, as shown in the same table, the Grade 11 HUMSS D learners obtained a mean score of 10.15 interpreted as 'Below Basic' in their pre-test while 14.99 interpreted as 'Basic' in their post-test. The result showed that after applying the intervention, the level of the speaking skill of the Grade 11 HUMSS D learners of DFLOMNHHS determined effectively. From having a 'Below Basic' level of speaking skill to 'Basic' level. The result is consistent with the article written by Pamolango, 2016 entitled, 'An Analysis of the Fillers Used by Asian Students in Busan, South Korea: A Comparative Study' which revealed that in order to answer the English questions, all of the Asian students used fillers.

Furthermore, as shown in the same table, in the pretest, two of them obtained scores ranging from 21-25 with 5% interpreted as 'Advanced'. It is observed as the highest percentage in the pretest which proves that these learners are good in public speaking. However, there are a total of 15 learners who obtained 37.5% in their pretest which was interpreted as 'developing' which means that these learners has the highest level of speaking skill. Hence, it was proven according to Jonsson (2016) that even native speakers occasionally have trouble finding the right words to use when speaking, and the less skilled the speaker is, the more communicational difficulties he or she will experience (Kaivanpanah, Yamouty, & Karami, 2012).

On the contrary, in their posttest, five of them obtained 12.5% which showed that there are three of them who excellently obtained 'advanced' after using the FRET Strategy. Moreover, as shown in the same table, there were no learners who obtained 'developing' remarks as 15 of them from the pretest were already advanced to 'below basic'. Thus, this clearly showed the effectiveness of using FRET Strategy. It also obtained the objective of the strategy where it is used as language improvement program that provides participants with the confidence to talk clearly and expound on their views (Gandeza, 2023).

Effectiveness of FRET Strategy in improving the Speaking Skill

As presented in the table 1, the mean score of the post-test is 14.99 which were interpreted as 'Basic'. This only means that the intervention was effective in improving the speaking skill of the Grade 11 HUMSS D learners of DFLOMNHHS. This was comparable with (Gandeza, 2023) claim that using language fillers in student discussions is a valuable strategy for synthesizing information and fostering a more engaging and coherent conversation where these fillers act as connective threads, weaving together various ideas seamlessly. In reality, as they use fillers, they are mentally thinking the next word/s they want to convey.

Furthermore, a saturation process of an online interview was also done to support solely the effectiveness of FRET Strategy as an intervention. Hence, the following themes were derived;

Fillers as Expressiveness

This highlights the significance of using fillers to convey information and to freely speak the English language in an utterance. This supports the claim of Gandeza, 2023 that language fillers serves as guideposts, directing the flow of discussion and helping listeners navigate through complex topics with greater ease. The implication here is that the use of FRET Strategy helped the respondents in expressing their thoughts well. This is also showed that fillers could really help learners or each individual in expressing themselves using English language. Hence, in using fillers, it could be of great help not only to expressing the idea, thoughts of information being stocked on mind of an individual but also effective in delivering an efficient and well-constructed thought. The following are responses provided by student participants;

“By using FRET STRATEGY I was able to think for the next ideas or word I am going to utter. Even though i wasn't able to elucidate the topic directly, I am still able to utter more words that can explain what the topic is all about”.

“(I) use the FRET strategy to come up with the idea, and to know what (word/s) are you going to say next. Express yourself in a way you can be more at ease and for them to understand you.”

“Express yourself in a way you can be more at ease and for them to understand you. Use fret to improve your speaking anxiety and to look or to think about the positive outcome.”

Fillers are Natural

The respondents reported encountering fillers naturally, which means they have been using fillers unintentionally. This proved that Gandeza, 2022 was true when he said that language fillers find comfort in using as companions, providing them with the linguistic assurance needed to articulate thoughts fluently and expand on ideas. To support this claim, in the study of Pamolango, 2016, in reality, Filipinos has the most number of utterances. It showed that students from Philippines produced the highest number of fillers, with the number of occurrences 58. Whereas, it also proves that Asian students are using fillers in order to answer the English questions. Additionally, it underscores its importance of embracing fillers naturally as it helps them to effectively convey an idea, information, thoughts and/or feelings. The following are responses provided by the students;

“I think its natural, because I can't stop myself in doing that or in using fillers”

“using language fillers is normal and there's nothing wrong in using it as long as you can expound or elucidate what you really wanted to say.”

Fillers as Concentration

This suggests that with the use of language fillers, any person who has speaking anxiety could concentrate to what they really want to convey despite of nervousness. This finding implies that with the use of FRET Strategy, the respondents were able to concentrate and mitigate nervousness. According to Gandeza 2022, language fillers aid in the orchestration of emotions, allowing individuals to present ideas, knowledge, and concepts with precision while mitigating feelings of nervousness. Notably, participants seamlessly incorporate language fillers into their everyday conversations. Below are some of the answers of the student participants;

“It help(ed) me through to be more specific about my thoughts, ideas and feeling(s). Through being concentrate into something you really want to express or convey.”

“And by doing the FRET Strategy, I was able to mitigate the nervousness”

Fillers as Confidence

Public Speaking was a hindrance for most people to speak because they don't have that confidence in speaking to large number of people or even to small audiences. When utilized judiciously and not excessively, filler

words can be a valuable ally for English learners, contributing to their linguistic proficiency. Participants express that these fillers contribute to a sense of ease and comfort during speech. Importantly, they attribute their enhanced fluency and confidence in using English language in the strategic use of fillers, as highlighted by (Basurto and Santos, 2011). Hence, if everyone could have the tenacity to speak confidently, they wouldn't encounter more fillers. Below are some of the responses of student participants;

"I believe that FRET STRATEGY is effective for me and us because this kept us improve our speaking anxiety, We are able to speak words that we want to tell, generate some ideas that could be the next topic of our words and prepared enough to utter some words that we want to tell. Therefore FRET STRATEGY had a big impact in order for us to improve our speaking anxiety"

"Well as a shy type person, FRET STRATEGY is highly effective in improving my speaking anxiety especially when delivering my speech to the crowd. FRET Strategy helps me build my confidence, reduce my nervousness and I think it helps me deliver more impactful presentation."

Fillers as Processor

Language fillers are still part of the work in progress for people who are flourishing from public speaking (Gandeza, 2023). Hence, this assured the claim of Gandeza, 2023 that fillers can also be used as time-creating devices. Hence, this also proves that fillers could help the speaker in having enough time to think for the next word to utter. When fillers are used to process information, it would be beneficial for students to strictly monitor their usage of it. However, if it helps them to think critically, positive and negative aspects shall be considered; (1) if it was used unnecessarily, speaker shall take into consideration practicing speaking the language. (2) If used unintentionally, speaker shall be mindful of its usage to avoid disruptions. Further, below are some of the responses of participants;

"By using some fillers which helps me to process the next word i am going to say."

"Everytime I use language fillers, it gives me time to think even if it's just for a second(s)" which indicates that to use fillers are naturally a processor and was effective to convey your message."

"Everytime when I don't know what the word, I was going to tell and uttered because this strategy leads me to the way of processing and generating ideas"

Fillers as Circumvent

The strategic use of language fillers in student discussions goes beyond mere stylistic choices; where it is a deliberate approach to enhancing the clarity, coherence, and engagement in conversations. (Gandeza, 2022) Hence, fillers are most likely to be used as circumvention in communication when the speaker cannot express his/her thoughts, feelings or ideas. Below is the response of the respondent;

"We used Language Filler to avoid miscommunication and to express how we feel, so to communicate properly it's better to ask if you do not understand it, so that you can express yourself more at ease and more clearly"

Fillers as a Teacher

Fillers are used to know what the next words to be uttered were and how it is used in communication. It simply taught learners to be an effective speaker just by using FRET Strategy or simply language fillers. As cited in the study of Erten, 2014, According to Nakatani, fillers are useful as it emphasizes the importance of knowing the learners' awareness of strategies when encountering communication problems. Hence, fillers are a good teacher in communication process for it teaches the speaker to effectively convey his/her message. As Krashen's 1998 Affective Filter embodies the view of 'affective variables' which plays a facilitative but non-causal role in second language acquisition. It also enables speakers to express what they have in mind at a particular point in a conversation, without fully displaying their thinking. Below are some of the responses of the students participants;

"Since I am not 100% in Speaking fluently in English, I always try my best to express myself in English Language to enhance more and improve more in my speaking (anxiety) because when you try and try you always learned and be better."

With the results shown above, it is seen that the use of FRET Strategy as an intervention to aid the learners' problem in speaking skill was effective. These probe the researcher in developing and designing a Conceptual Model in Using FRET Strategy which will be used by pre-service teachers if they opt to conduct the same study. Moreover, the designed model was utilized by the researcher during teaching internship which led him in developing it for future researches and/or references of student teachers if they find the same gap.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model in Using FRET Strategy

Figure 1 shows the conceptual model in using FRET Strategy at DFLOMNHHS. This model mainly highlights the processes that the researcher followed. The processes are dubbed as **FILL** in using FRET Strategy whereas: *Following Most Essential Learning Competencies*, *Identifying Learners Speaking Ability*, *Letter of Approval*, *Let learners use FRET in delivering their answers*.

As pre-service teacher in the implementation of FRET Strategy, understanding the most essential learning competencies on how it is used and taught, Identifying the speaking ability of learners prior to reflecting for the letter of approval to conduct and implementing what were learned from the lessons and/or discussions are important process that needs to be followed. The succeeding discussion explained the things that should be followed in using the model.

Following Most Essential Learning Competencies. The first step that the researcher followed in using FRET Strategy was to follow the Most Essential Learning Competencies. To do this, the researcher discussed, analyzed the lesson/s taught and understood these aspects with the help of his cooperating teacher to effectively analyze and understand the techniques they used in teaching the learners. Through this, the MELCs are carefully understood and followed for effective implementation.

Identifying Learners Speaking Ability. After understanding and following the most essential learning competencies, the assigned teacher shall monitor the learners on how they speak, specifically, their strengths and

weaknesses. Some of the salient observations are learners have difficulty in speaking English and is distress in expressing themselves in English language, learners are good in writing skills yet they cannot fully express themselves in speaking English language. Notably, the strategy was just part of the monitoring, reflecting, and implementation

Letter of Approval. This process required the researcher to coordinate and asked for the conduct of the FRET Strategy to the Secondary School Principal IV of DFLOMNHS. Here, the action research was submitted for approval and it was reflected through questions asked by the Principal to the researcher. Through this process, pertinent assistance was given to the researcher in strong adherence of the protocols followed by the school.

Let Learners use FRET Strategy in delivering their Answers. Once approved, the researcher implemented the FRET Strategy in various aspects such as speech delivery as their main lesson for the second quarter to maximize the participation of the students in the teaching-learning process. Collaboration, reflection, and monitoring are being employed before, during, and after the conduct of the FRET Strategy. In employing this strategy, the researcher articulated that the success of FRET Strategy was observed.

Implications for Teachers and Learners

The utilization of FRET Strategy inside the Teaching-Learning process brings forward transformative recommendations for both teachers and learners. For teachers, it requires collaborative learning, proficient assistance in public speaking skills, and a persistent cycle of reflection and alteration. On the other hand, learners are locked in with energetic back, collaborative of learning, honing critical thinking and communication skills, grasping cooperative learning, cultivating self-awareness, and benefiting from persistent feedback and self-reflection. This synergy between teachers and learners underpins a move from traditional education to a dynamic, learner-centric paradigm that develops engagement, critical thought, and down to earth application of information.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Grade 11 students faced numerous difficulties when it comes to speaking, writing, and comprehending English language. Challenges such as difficulty in choosing the right words to be used, speaking in front of many people which causes significant anxiety. This study highlights the multifaceted nature of using FRET Strategy as an intervention. Hence, with the indicated results, the following conclusions were drawn: (1)The level of the speaking skill improved effectively after applying the intervention, (2) There is a significant difference between the level of speaking skill of the learners in the pre-test and post-test, (3) The use of FRET Strategy in improving the speaking skill was effective, and (4) The emergence of implementing the Conceptual Model in Using FRET Strategy calls for the conduct of the same study that shall look into it in the light of various research variables.

As per the results of this study, there are a few specific suggestions for students, teachers, and administrators to reduce and alleviate anxiety related to speaking English language and using FRET Strategy as an intervention at DFLOMNHS. First is the implementation of FRET Strategy to improve the speaking skill of the learners to continually improve public education. By doing this, it highlights the effectiveness of the aforementioned Conceptual Model if tested and used. Second, teachers that use English as a medium of instruction may incorporate FRET Strategy into their lesson especially in Oral Communication subject, public speaking or during teaching-learning process to allow the learners in using language fillers instead of allowing them to speak in vernacular or in Filipino language. By doing this, students and teachers will be able to practice speaking the language as it is beneficial in the future of each students, especially that they are in the Senior High School. Third, the school shall follow mechanisms in implementing FRET Strategy; however, the study possesses various limitations. First, the developed conceptual model though validated and affirmed during procedures. Second, the study was confined into one school and one section; thus, the creation of the conceptual model which is only applicable to the locale of the study. Fourth, a similar study in a wider coverage is needed to be conducted in which the output of the study should be implemented and evaluated in terms of its effectiveness to determine if the same

findings will be established. And lastly, a study that will test the effectiveness of the intervention in improving the speaking skill of the learners in other languages may be conducted to determine if the same findings will be achieved. By implementing these recommendations, students and teachers could collaborate to create a more supportive and inclusive environment where English language is acknowledged, addressed, and minimized, ultimately enhancing the language learning experience for all students.

REFERENCES

- Bodie, G. D. (2009, December 14). A Racing Heart, Rattling Knees, and Ruminative Thoughts: Defining, Explaining, and Treating Public Speaking Anxiety. *Communication Education*, 1.
- Gandeza, C. C. (2023, July 11). Language Fillers Used by Students in Conversation. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 4(2), 551.
- Gandeza, C. C. (2023, July 11). Language Fillers Used by Students in Conversation. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 542.
- Gandeza, C. C. (2023, July 11). Language Fillers Used by Students in Conversation. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 543.
- Gandeza, C. C. (2023, July 11). Language Fillers Used by Students in Conversation. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 542.
- Gandeza, C. C. (2023). Use of FRET: Language Fillers Strategy Enhancement in Oral DIscourse. 2.
- Hashemi. (2020, January). Public Speaking Anxiety in the Thai EFL Context. *LEARNJournal : Language Education and Acquisition Research Network Journal*, 13(1), 197.
- Lungay, I. R. (2023, June 12). Public Speaking Anxiety in Oral Communication Among Grade 11 Students of PHINMA-COC. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 2.
- Lungay, I. R. (2023, June 12). Public Speaking Anxiety in Oral Communication Among Grade 11 Students of PHINMA-COC. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 5.
- Mulyani, S. (2018). Investigating Factors Causing Students' Anxiety in Speaking English. *International Journal in Applied Linguistics of Parahikma*, 1, 1.
- Mulyani, S. (2018). Investigating Factors Causing Students' Anxiety in Speaking English. *International Journal in Applied Linguistics of Parahikma*, 1(1).
- Pamolango, V. A. (2016). An Analysis of the Fillers Used by Asian Students in. *International Journal of Languages, Literature and Linguistics*, 98.
- Raja, F. (2017, June 17). Anxiety Level in Students of Public Speaking: Causes and Remedies. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 4(1), 1.